

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ASSERTIVENESS AND JOB-RELATED STRESS, CONFLICT
MANAGEMENT IN NURSES**¹Sarfranz Masih, ²Sana Sehar, ³Muhammad Afzal, ⁴Dr. Syed Amir Gilani¹Student: The University of Lahore., ²Assistant Professor: The University of Lahore., ³Associate professor: The University of Lahore., ⁴Dean faculty of allied sciences. The University of Lahore.**Article Received:** October 2019 **Accepted:** November 2019 **Published:** December 2019**Abstract:**

In the start of nursing career students have insufficient preparation and some intrapersonal conflict about profession and in general practice. Assertiveness education and assertion of skill is very important for nursing student to be master for everything and have good strong insight for problem/situation. During clinical rotation the nurse instructor can prepare the students about Some e styles for conflict management and aspects related with understanding of problem how to manage it with assertiveness. In another study conducted in Hong Kong in china to evaluate the conflict management style in undergraduate students. Study finding shows most of student manage their conflicts with their instructors by using collaborating style for conflict management and used competing style of conflict management least frequently

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Please cite this article in press Sarfranz Masih et al., *Assertiveness And Job Related Stress, Conflict Management In Nurses., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(12).*

INTRODUCTION:

Assertiveness is quality of being self-assured and confident and ability to express own feelings, opinions, emotions and thoughts in good open manner while cares the others respect and believes and care other rights. assertiveness is key component for built a reliable relationship among team mates, coworkers, towards care consumer, between organization and staff, to promote a healthy and safe conflict free work environment. (Aysel A. Ozdemir., 2018).

Also conflict management is intrapersonal skill some people have naturally and some have adapted it from their educational environment.conflict management among nursing student and managers/supervisor on patient allocations and in non-nursing task and shortage of staff in department and main issue the absenteeism of staff without informing is very crucial. (Arieli.,2013).

In the start of nursing career students have insufficient preparation and some intrapersonal conflict about profession and in general practice. Assertiveness education and assertion of skill is very important for nursing student to be master for everything and have good strong insight for problem/situation. During clinical rotation the nurse instructor can prepare the students about Some e styles for conflict management and aspects related with understanding of problem how to manage it with assertiveness. (RofidaMagedAbd El-Rehman., 2018).

Nurses are repetitively contact with health work team and coworker and many care consumers on daily basis and they spent most of the time with public interaction, patients because it is the profession demand. Therefore, nurses need to more assertive in their profession to provide quality care or coordinate in continue of care. nurses need to good clear assertive and conflict free communication skills to complete her/his job accuracy. (WafaAbd El Hazem Honsy.,2018).

Some main conflict management styles are very important in problem solving through negotiation skills, effective communication skills of collaborating, skills ofaccommodating, skills of competing, skills of compromising and avoiding. persons who use these skills can manage the conflict in direct manners and can survive in critical situation and find out possible solution for active issues and manage them in good manners with collaborating skills. With the skills of accommodating face conflicts in passive way and follow decision of others. (Manal Hassan.,2017)

CASE PRESENTATION:**Scenario:**

Once in a public hospital in emergency department in the presence of the manager of emergency department a patient admitted in critical condition there was need to pass ETT tube to the patient. The laryngoscope was not in working well and the on duty doctor shouted at staff due to inappropriate equipment. Family members of the patients were also shouted and showing their aggression. The situation was uncontrolled to manage. All this situation was created due to the negligence of the manager because the manager was not able to perform her duties well and not able to assess that the instruments were in working condition or not. I have already seen that the manager of emergency department has poor communication skills and assertive behavior. She was unable to deliver her ideas, opinions and views in a strong, confident and assertive manner. There were lots of conflicts developed over there due to the poor management of the management. After that, on duty doctor carried this situation to the higher authorities.

RESULTS:

In this scenario there was a lack of practical skills and management skills lack of effective communication and poor check and balance in ward equipment and limited alternative options. Lack of self- confidence and poor staff coordination in task allocations. A lot of organizational managerial conflicts between staff and management lack of coordination. lack of mutual understanding and poor critical thinking. Negligence and poor clinical practice and managerial issues. lack of organizational interest in ongoing situation. Lack of education and lack of assertiveness and trust among team. Manager was not competent in her work and unable the lead code blue situation. She was bothered with this situation and wasn't able to manage situation well and may have organizational power issues.

Conflict management:

In this scenario conflict management was seen which was created due to

- Inadequate communication
- Incorrect facts
- Lack of trust
- Unclear position description
- Misunderstanding of roles and responsibilities
- Unstable leadership
- Power issues (Finkelman, 1996, p.1-1:17)

Conflict Management: Issues and Strategies:

Conflict management is critical in any organization.

When conflicts arise then managers and staff need to understand conflict management issues and strategies. The major goals of conflict management are:

1. To eliminate or decrease the conflict
2. To meet the needs of the patient, family/significant others, and the organization
3. To ensure that all parties feel positive about the resolution so that future work together can be productive.

When staff experience conflict, powerless and empowerment, as well as aggressiveness and passive – aggressiveness, become important.

DISCUSSION:

People with less low of worth have difficulty in standing themselves because they view others thoughts, feelings and more imperative than own insight on situation. Assertiveness and non-assertiveness behaviors are result of cognitive frame which control the person response on critical condition. these cognitive insight frames of critical situations are guided by central beliefs, which develop from childhood environment experience, view of self, other respect and dignity, relationship with others (safaa et al.,2017).

Assertiveness is key component for success in any department but in nursing department without this skill individual nurse can't get their professional status or empowerment. Assertiveness is human response, It is insight of a person and everyone have in his/her personality, it confirmed with individual mutual understanding,insight on a scenario, individual thoughts and beliefs, by expression of emotions and reaction on a critical situation and social cues. some developed countries have planned assertiveness education programs for their next generations students, and they reschedule their education curricula.

Assertiveness and conflict management is very essential among nursing students because most of the student come from nursing institutes with different fears, experiences, expectations, background, attitudes, aspirations can lead to conflict and cues. Conflicts are result of human communication responses. In the presence of conflict between new nurses and nurse instructor produce some negative and positive feedbacks or conflicts which can reduce with assertiveness and conflict management skill and education. Use some techniques of negotiation to solve the interpersonal and intrapersonal conflicts. Negative feedbacks or conflicts are including stress among staffs, weak interpersonal relationship, lack of interest in ongoing activities and major negative

feedback or psychomotor response is increase in absenteeism (McKibben., 2017).

In other hand assertiveness use for management of conflicts regarding critical situations that were not manage with good and professional manners can cause stress, anger, frustration, stressors factors which leads to a mental health problem in individual. Assertiveness enables a individual reduce personal anxiety, improve relationship with other and respect the others rights and have ability to understand the facts of reality, able to cope with stress and set his/her actual domains for life (Shiferaw et al., 2015).

In a study findings highest percentage of novice nurses and students are used the compromising style to reduce the conflicts and some are used collaborating styles to reduce their conflicts with the nurse instructors. Lowest percentage of the novice nurses and students are used the competing styles of conflict management due to the novice nurses and student nurses have strong interpersonal relationship with instructor. students have good effective communication skill with instructor and try to find out actual problem and try to solve it with exchange of right information among student and instructor. In other hand instructor have authority as in faculty and student have less chance to challenge them and less chance to use aggressive conflict management style (Krautscheid et al., 2017).

In another study conducted in Hong Kong in china to evaluate the conflict management style in undergraduate students. Study finding shows most of student manage their conflicts with their instructors by using collaborating style for conflict management and used competing style of conflict management least frequently(Chan et al., 2014).

Recommendation:

1. Instructors should instruct and educate the students manage their conflicts effectively and in good professional manners and provide assertiveness training programs workshops to reduce the conflicts and general practice hesitations.
2. Good and effective task allocations regarding validity of ward instrument and close check and balance on daily basis to prevent from errors.
3. Enhance effective communication skills among nurses and others team mates and promote trust and reliable relationship between blue code team.
4. Promote education level and give authority to high educated and deserved people to get good managerial results.
5. Create assertiveness educational structure and

environment for students and arrange program that promote assertive education in future.

6. Nurse instructor should arrange the workshops to teach coping techniques and manage stress to nursing students.
7. Nurse instructor should motivate the student to express the thoughts and feeling and opinions in open good manners and cares about others right, respect and dignity others of beliefs.
8. Nurse instructor should provide a safe healthy and learning environment with freedom of thought opinions and feelings and reactions and denies on social cues.
9. Nurse educator should enhance the power of listening and effective communication skills of student.
10. Arrange nursing program for nurse's education and enhancement of professional skills and self-esteem, self-assertion and improve communication skills.
11. Assertiveness techniques and education include in undergraduate nursing curriculum to produce assertive nurses in clinical setup and promote the quality of care in health care setting.
12. Study of the relationship among assertive nurses, managers, supervisor and other co-worker method of act towards critical situation and coping strategies.

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